

Permafrost Management Through City Planning and Design: Linking Observations to Snow, Meltwater, and Infrastructure Practices in Utqiagvik, Alaska

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Barrow Utilities and Electric Cooperative Inc. (BUECI)
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Introduction

Arctic urban environments remain under-studied and under-observed, even though surface modifications associated with development, construction, and city maintenance practices can exert significant control on permafrost stability at parcel and infrastructure scales. Snow and meltwater management, alteration of natural drainage, construction practices, introduction of fill materials, and anthropogenic heat sources in developed areas are rarely resolved in regional monitoring programs, yet they directly shape maintenance decisions and longer-term planning (Klene et al., 2013; Jones et al., 2025). The relative contribution of these factors to permafrost thermal regimes in the built environment remains poorly constrained.

This statement presents selected results from two complementary projects focused on urban permafrost in Utqiagvik, Alaska: an NSF Navigating the New Arctic (NNA) project (#2022639; 2021–2026) and a UVA Environmental Institute Climate Collaborative project initiated in 2024. Together, the projects integrate environmental sensors, numerical modeling, and remote sensing with planning- and design strategies that prioritize managing snow and surface water to support permafrost stability. Two interdisciplinary design studios at the University of Virginia School of Architecture—City Built on Thawing Ground (Fall 2024; Fall 2025)—served as applied research platforms, combining field observations, analysis of meteorological and ground-based sensor data, *in situ* thaw probing, and engagement with partner organizations to develop an understanding of priority areas of permafrost and key development issues within the community and across scales.

Observations linking surface conditions to permafrost response

Data from the NNA observing network (2022–2025) show consistent summer contrasts between urban and tundra sites. Both air and near-surface ground temperatures are higher at urban sites than at the Barrow Environmental Observatory control site, and warmer on southern and western sides of buildings than on northern and eastern sides. Analysis of the data indicates that air temperature, solar radiation, and aspect are the dominant predictors of ground temperatures in summer. Soil moisture effects are seasonal, with wetter soils being slightly cooler in summer and warmer in fall, cooling more slowly as the fall freeze progresses.

As part of the 2024 and 2025 design studios, one week field components in Utqiagvik provided opportunities for teams of 4-5 students to carry out detailed observations linking surface conditions to permafrost response at parcel and infrastructure-segment scales. Active layer depth, ponding and drainage patterns, ground material composition, vegetation, and topographic controls were documented through thaw probing, systematic photo transects, and georeferenced field notes.

Caption: Permafrost vulnerability map developed for Utqiagvik based on topography, drainage, and urban activity/development. (Source: Arctic Design Group Studio, *City Built on Thawing Ground*. J. Fong, A. Bell, Y. Shuai, 2024).

Implementable strategies for maintenance and development

The studios produced design and management strategies deployable by partner organizations. A key result of this work was to reframe Utqiagvik's urban hydrology as a network of sub-

watersheds defined by the interactions between blocks, topography, culverts, buildings, and infrastructure—supporting decisions based on upstream and downstream effects across coherent hydrologic units rather than administrative boundaries, and identifying areas of permafrost vulnerability.

Building on analysis of existing permafrost conditions—including areas of thermokarst, flooding, snow drifting, and drainage—the studios also developed housing designs responding to city comprehensive planning documents and partner input, with the goal of reducing impacts on natural drainage pathways and integrating above-grade utilities as multifunctional elements of neighborhoods.

Several strategies were structured as phased development coupling geomorphic and hydrological processes at multiple scales: at the residential scale, low-cost practices to maintain culverts and minimize pooling and drifting; at the block scale, managed seasonal snow accumulation to create self-deepening drainage channels that simulate polygonal tundra microtopography; and at the city scale, with planning approaches that align new above-grade infrastructure with tundra watershed patterns.

Implications for Arctic observing systems

Environmental and permafrost observing strategies for Arctic settlements should be organized at scales that enable municipal and borough organizations to act—parcels, infrastructure networks, watersheds, and planning zones. Key observation types include repeatable low-cost field methods linked to GIS datasets; integration of *in situ* measurements with remote sensing of snow and surface water; and development of observing “report cards” that translate collected data into maintenance practices, siting decisions, and support for state or federal funding applications.

Recommendations to AOS 2026

1. **Prioritize the urban permafrost domain.** Establish Arctic settlements as critical observing sites within pan-Arctic monitoring networks. Monitoring must move beyond undisturbed reference sites to quantify how anthropogenic drivers—snow redistribution, drainage modification, surface materials, and heat inputs—dictate ground thermal response at scales relevant to planning and maintenance.
2. **Coordinate cross-scale observations for municipal planning.** Integrate ground-based sensors, thaw probing, maintenance records, and remote sensing within urban frameworks applicable across Arctic settlements. Ensure observing resolves variability at scales aligned with municipal land-use planning and infrastructure management.
3. **Standardize data for municipal integration.** Deliver permafrost observations as GIS-ready, interoperable geospatial layers with consistent spatial referencing and metadata, enabling direct integration into municipal asset management systems and capital improvement planning.
4. **Deploy design-based monitoring models.** Formalize interdisciplinary field programs—such as university design studios—as repeatable models for applied permafrost monitoring that bridge scientific observation and local governance by producing spatial analyses and design and visualization tools for infrastructure planning and funding.

Selected references

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